

Code for generating MoCHAT

The **Monthly CMIP6-downscaled High-resolution (1 km) near-surface Air Temperature** projections (MoCHAT) include mean temperature (*tas*), maximum temperature (*tasmax*), minimum temperature (*tasmin*) of 16 diverse General Climate Models (GCMs) and Multi-Model Ensemble of all 16 GCMs. The temporal ranges include the historical period (1970-2014) and three future emission scenarios (2015-2100), i.e., SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP5-8.5.

This document provides an overview of the code implementing the **Delta Downscaling Method** for generating MoCHAT dataset.

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Input Datasets

1. **Historical Climate Data:** WorldClim version 2.1 monthly climate data for the period 1970-2000. This dataset serves as the baseline reference for historical temperatures (<https://www.worldclim.org/data/worldclim21.html>).
2. **Coarse-Resolution GCM Data:** NASA Earth Exchange Global Daily Downscaled Projections (NEX-GDDP-CMIP6), which provides coarse-resolution (0.25°) temperature data (<https://www.nccs.nasa.gov/services/data-collections/land-based-products/nex-gddp-cmip6>).
3. **Target Variables:** Mean Temperature (*tas*), maximum Temperature (*tasmax*) and minimum Temperature (*tasmin*)
4. **Temporal range:** Historical (1970–2014) and future scenarios (2015–2100) (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5)

Table 1. Description of selected models and their information in the NEX-GDDP-CMIP6 dataset.

NEX-GDDP-CMIP6	
Model	Total 16 models: ACCESS-CM2, ACCESS-ESM1-5, CanESM5, CMCC-ESM2, EC-Earth3, EC-Earth3-Veg-LR, GFDL-ESM4, INM-CM4-8, INM-CM5-0, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MIROC6, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MPI-ESM1-2-LR, MRI-ESM2-0, NorESM2-LM, NorESM2-MM
Variant	r1i1p1f1
Simulation	Historical (1970–2014) SSP1-2.6 (2015–2100) SSP2-4.5 (2015–2100) SSP5-8.5 (2015–2100)
Variable	<i>tas</i> , <i>tasmax</i> , <i>tasmin</i>
Temporal Coverage	1970-01-01–2100-12-31
Temporal Resolution	Daily
Spatial Resolution	$0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$

Method

Step 1: Generate Monthly Time Series Temperature Dataset for NEX-GDDP-CMIP6

This step involves extracting the monthly temperature time series from the NEX-GDDP-CMIP6 dataset for the period from 1970 to 2100. The raw data from NEX-GDDP-CMIP6 (0.25°) will be used as input. **Main steps:**

- 1) Extract monthly temperature data (*tas*, *tasmax*, *tasmin*) of specified GCM for the period 1970-2100.
- 2) Store the data in a time series format for further processing.

Step 2: Calculate Historical Climatology Averages (1970–2000) for NEX-GDDP-CMIP6

In this step, historical climatology averages for the period 1970–2000 are calculated using the NEX-GDDP-CMIP6 dataset. These averages are used as the baseline for comparison with future projections. **Main steps:**

- 1) Compute the average temperature for each month from 1970 to 2000.
- 2) Store these climatology averages for use in calculations.

Step 3: Compute Coarse-Resolution Delta Change Time Series Data

The change time series data is calculated by comparing monthly temperature averages with those of historical monthly climatology averages. This produces the “delta” for each variable. **Main steps:**

- 1) For each climate variable (*tas*, *tasmax*, *tasmin*), subtract historical monthly climatology averages from the corresponding monthly time series average (1970–2100).
- 2) This change data represents the difference between future and historical temperature conditions.
- 3) The result is a set of values that will be adjusted by WorldClim dataset.

Step 4: Bilinear Interpolation to Create High Spatial Resolution Delta Change Dataset

In this step, the change time series data from the previous step (which is at a coarse resolution, 0.25°) is interpolated to a higher spatial resolution (~1 km) using bilinear interpolation. **Main steps:**

- 1) Perform bilinear interpolation on the coarse-resolution change data.
- 2) The output will be a high-resolution (~1 km) change dataset, which represents the change in temperature across a finer spatial grid.

Step 5: Integrate Delta Change Data with WorldClim for Final Downscaled Temperature Dataset

In the final step, the high-resolution change dataset is integrated with the baseline WorldClim dataset to produce a fine spatial resolution temperature dataset for the period 1970 to 2100. This step allows for generating downscaled temperature projections at higher spatial resolution. **Main steps:**

- 1) Add the delta values to the baseline WorldClim temperature data.
- 2) Produce the final high-resolution temperature dataset that spans the years 1970 to 2100.